

A Comparative Study of Supervisory Practices of Head teachers of Public and Private Basic Schools in Koforidua, Eastern Region

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Abstract

The study is a descriptive survey that is aimed at comparing supervisory practices of headteachers of public and private basic schools in Koforidua. The study adopted quantitative approach in data collection and analysis. The population for the study constituted headteachers and teachers of the six (6) selected public basic schools (Koforidua Presbyterian 'A' and 'B' streams and Riis Presby JHS) and private basic schools (Pentecost Preparatory School, Madonna Preparatory School and King Jesus Prep. School) in Koforidua in the New Juaben Municipality of the Eastern Region of Ghana. Meanwhile, through purposive sampling technique, sixty (60) respondents (teachers and headteachers) were selected for the study. This comprised of six (6) headteachers and fifty-four (54) teachers. Structured questionnaire was the main research instrument. Data collected using a questionnaire was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). In the light of the findings, the study concluded that the differences in classroom support given to teachers in the public and private basic schools in Koforidua were that teachers in private schools receive feedback on supervision and also TLMs are available for use in the classroom. Again, on the opportunities and support given to pupils in performing their instructional supervisory roles in public and private basic schools in Koforidua, it was concluded that public school pupils lack some opportunities and support such as learning with and manipulating TLMs, access to school facilities and motivation from parents. The following recommendations were made based on the conclusion drawn; (i) Headteachers' in public school teachers are advised to give feedback on supervision to their teachers and (iii) The Ministry of Education and Ghana Education Service should provide teaching and learning materials for teachers to use in the classroom.

Key Words: *Supervision of Instruction, Curriculum, Academic Performance, Leadership, Feedback.*

Introduction

Supervision of instruction is a key part of the headteacher's role in ensuring that the planned activities are being effectively implemented in the classroom (Şahin, 2011). Zepeda (2003) contends that instructional supervision refers to the continuous monitoring of classroom teaching with the aim of not only promoting professional practices, but also to enhance professional development in a collegial and collaborative style. Research suggests that supervision needs to take place in a professional environment which values instructors' contributions and promotes experimentation (Blasé & Blasé, 2004; Glickman, Gorden, & Ross-Gordon, 2004). It is seen as a positive democratic action aimed at not only improvement of classroom instruction but also creating a harmonious environment through continued growth of all concerned; the child, the teacher, the supervisor, the parent and the administration. Access to basic education has improved rapidly throughout the developing world since 1990, but learning outcomes have lagged behind (World Bank, 2002, UNESCO, 2007).

In Ghana, basic education is provided in partnership by the government, communities, parents, private entrepreneurs and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs). Teachers' acceptance and interaction with the instructional supervision practices like techniques, models or process, methods used by headteachers at school, provide the catalyst for performance improvement. Supervision is an interactive process that depends on the source of supervision, the supervisor and the teacher (Ebmeier, 2003).

Today's instructional supervisory practices are borrowed from the earlier American education system in which schooling was in the hands of local authorities. The supervisory practices were concerned with management of schools and the fulfillment of the prescribed curricular needs rather than the improvement of teaching and

learning process. It was referred to as inspection due to its autocratic nature. This is co-related to instructional supervision that are mostly conducted by the headteachers today (Nelson & Hammeram, 1996 as cited in Wambui, 2015).

There is an indication that all countries feel the need for supervision in order to check school functioning. Many countries like Ghana from 1990s onwards have attempted to reform supervision in order to make it more effective. Supervision is a key tool to monitor and improve the quality of education. Schools can make a difference to pupils' achievement through the headteacher's supervisory leadership. It is the headteacher who sets the pace, leading and motivating the staff and pupils' to perform to their best (Circuit Supervisor' Handbook, 2002). This means the quality of leadership in a school determines the way students perform. Instructional supervision is a collaborative effort between the headteacher and the teachers which call for mutual understanding between the two parties (Circuit Supervisor' Handbook, 2002).

In Ghana, a number of studies have investigated the nature of instructional supervision of headteachers in the basic schools (Amina, 2015; Ankomah, 2002; Baffour-Awuah, 2019). Ankomah (2002) for instance found out that one of the characteristics of successful private schools in Ghana was the presence of strong leadership exhibited through supervision. The study noted that in most successful private schools, the headteachers visit classrooms during instructional time and provided feedback to teachers.

Table 4.1: Comparison Between Performance of Public and Private Basic Schools in Koforidua Using New Juaben South Municipality BECE Analysis/League Table

Schools	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
	Percentage Passed %				
Presby 'A' JHS	84	75	78	85	76
Presby 'B' JHS	79	62	84	72	70
Riss Presby JHS	78	80	89	72	74
Pentecost School	100	100	100	100	100
Modonna School	98	100	96	100	100
King Jesus School	100	100	100	100	100

Source: BECE Analysis/League Table for Schools in New Juaben South Municipality, 2015-2019.

The performances of these selected public and private Basic Schools in the Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) for the past five years have comparatively been different. Most private schools were ranked higher than the public schools and instructional supervision is one key factor identified to influence the performances of pupils (BECE Analysis/League Table, 2015-2019). Many factors could attribute to the differences in the performances. Meanwhile, recent studies focused on factors contributing to low academic performances of pupils in basic schools but little have been done on instructional supervision. This is because, for any institution or organization to function effectively and achieve its objectives, supervision must be effective and this is what craved the interest of the researcher to carry out this study, to compare the supervisory practices of headteachers of public and private basic schools in Koforidua, Eastern Region.

The following hypotheses served as a guide for the study.

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between classroom support given to teachers in the public and private basic schools in Koforidua.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between the opportunities and support given to pupils in performing their instructional supervisory roles in public and private basic schools in Koforidua.

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between training opportunities created for the teachers in public and private basic schools in Koforidua.

2.13 Conceptual Framework

The study is conceptualized on the fact that teachers instructional supervision practices lead to effective teaching, resulting to high academic achievement.

Figure 2.1: Headteachers' instructional supervision practices and their Influences on pupils 'performance

Methodology

The study is based on the systems theory whose proponent is biologist Ludwig Von Bertalanffy (1972) as cited by Apenteng (2012). The theory postulates that a school as a system is composed of various parts which work together interrelated for accomplishment of stated goals. A school exists in a form of an open system because it receives its inputs from the society and also empties its out puts back to the society. According to this theory, education has various parts; these include headteachers, teachers, pupils and parents. If one fails in his/her role then the system fails. A school receives teachers, pupils and parents from the society.

This study employed a descriptive survey, which is a type of research undertaken with the aim of describing characteristics of variables in a situation. According to Best and Khan (2009), descriptive research is concerned with conditions or relationships that exists, opinions that are held, processes that are going on, effects that are evident, or trends that are developing.

The population for the study constituted headteachers and teachers of the six (6) selected public basic schools (Koforidua Presbyterian 'A' and 'B' streams and Riis Presby JHS) and private basic schools (Pentecost Preparatory School, Madonna Preparatory School and King Jesus Prep. School) in Koforidua in the New Juaben Municipality of the Eastern Region of Ghana. The six schools have six (6) headteachers and fifty-four (54) teachers. This population size is made up of twenty-three (23) females and thirty-seven (37) males.

A sample drawn from a population refers to all possible cases of what the researcher is interested in studying and these are often people who have some particular characteristics in common (Asamoah-Gyimah & Duodu, 2007). Through purposive sampling technique, sixty (60) respondents (teachers and headteachers) were selected for the study. This comprised of six (6) headteachers and fifty-four (54) teachers. This sample size was justifiable because they represent the entire teachers in the six selected schools. The estimate sample size is 40 and the sample size estimation was done using Slovin's formula;

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N e^2}$$

Where; n- is the sample size

N – Is the total population (sum of all teachers in the school = 60)

e – Margin of error of 0.01% (confidence level of 99%)

$$n = \frac{60}{1 + \frac{60 \times 0.01^2}{60}}$$

$$n = \frac{60}{1 + \frac{60 \times 0.0001}{60}}$$

$$n = \frac{60}{1 + 0.006}$$

$$n = \frac{60}{1.006}$$

n = 59.642, Approximately, 60

Structured questionnaire was the main research instrument. The questionnaire was designed for both headteachers and teachers' containing two sections. Section A contain structured questions requesting for demographic data while section B contained both structured questions based on the research objectives. Both closed and open-ended statements were used because they specified all the possible responses for easy analysis and interpretation.

Results

Differences in classroom support given to teachers in the public and private basic schools in Koforidua

This chapter is focused on determining the differences in classroom support given to teachers in the public and private basic schools in Koforidua.

4.8: Teachers are regularly supervised by headteacher and officers

Valid	Scale	Public		Private	
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
	Strongly Disagree	3	10.0	3	10.0
	Disagree	5	16.7	1	3.3
	Agree	14	46.7	5	16.7
	Strongly Agree	8	26.7	21	70.0
	Total	30	100.0	30	100.0

Source: Field Data, November, 2020

In Table 4.8, 14 (46.7%) public school teachers agree and 8 (26.7%) of them strongly agree (mean score 4.33 and st deviation 1.295) that teachers are regularly supervised by headteacher and officers and this was supported by 86.7% of the private school teachers who either agree or strongly agree with a mean score of 3.63 and standard deviation of 1.325).

4.11: Teachers are given enough room to perform their duties without tension

Valid	Scale	Public		Private	
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
	Agree	4	13.3	9	30.0
	Strongly Agree	26	86.7	21	70.0
	Total	30	100.0	30	100.0

Source: Field Data, November, 2020

With a mean score of 4.70 and st deviation of .466, Table 4.11 reveals that all (100%) the public school teachers affirmed that they are given enough room to perform their duties without tension and this was also backed by (100%) of the private school teachers with a mean score of 4.86 and standard deviation of .345.

Differences in training opportunities created for the teachers in public and private basic schools in Koforidua

This aspect of the study is meant to assess the differences in training opportunities created for the teachers in public and private basic schools in Koforidua

Table 4.25: Teachers are given the opportunity to share ideas among themselves

	Scale	Public		Private	
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Valid	Agree	1	3.3	2	6.7
	Strongly Agree	29	96.7	28	93.3
Total		30	100.0	30	100.0

Source: Field Data, November, 2020

Likewise, results presented in Table 4.25 shows an agreement in the views expressed by teachers of both sides. The results indicates that 100% of all the respondents (public school teachers with a mean score of 4.93 and st. deviation of .253) and private school teachers (mean score of 4.966 and st. deviation of .182) were certain that teachers are given the opportunity to share ideas among themselves.

4.30: Teachers have negative perception towards supervisory practices in the school

	Scale	Public		Private	
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	2	6.7	0	0.0
	Disagree	8	26.7	0	0.0
	Neutral	2	6.7	8	26.7
	Agree	0	0.0	4	13.0
	Strongly Agree	18	60.0	18	60.0
Total		30	100.0	30	100.0

Source: Field Data, November, 2020

With a mean score of 4.33 and standard deviation of .884, 60% of the public school teachers in Table 4.30 strongly agree teachers have negative perception towards supervisory practices in the school and this was again seconded by 73% of the private school teachers with a mean score of 3.80 and standard deviation of 1.540.

Table 4.31: Most teachers do not cooperate with headteachers during supervision

	Scale	Public		Private	
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	6	20.0	0	0.0
	Disagree	0	0.0	2	6.7
	Neutral	5	16.7	6	20.0
	Agree	7	23.3	8	26.7
	Strongly Agree	12	40.0	14	46.7
Total		30	100.0	30	100.0

Source: Field Data, November, 2020

Similarly, another agreement was seen in Table 4.31 where 19 (63.3%) public school teachers maintained (mean 4.133, st. deviation .973) that most teachers do not cooperate with headteachers during supervision. Meanwhile, with a mean score of 3.63 and a standard deviation of 1.519, 73.4% of the private school teachers affirmed that most teachers do not cooperate with headteachers.

Table 4.32: Some headteachers' are not effective in carrying out instructional supervision

	Scale	Public		Private	
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	4	13.3	4	13.3

Disagree	1	3.3	7	23.3
Neutral	0	0.0	0	0.0
Agree	10	33.3	8	26.7
Strongly Agree	15	50.0	11	36.7
Total	30	100.0	30	100.0

Source: Field Data, November, 2020

Additionally, information presented in Table 4.32 posit that 10 (33.3%) public teachers agree and 15 (50%) others strongly agree (mean 3.50; st. deviation 1.525) that some headteachers' are not effective in carrying out instructional supervision and this was supported by 19 (63.4%) private school teachers with a mean score of 4.033; st. deviation of 1.376.

Table 4.33: Instructional supervision is time consuming

	Scale	Public		Private	
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	9	30.0	6	20.0
	Disagree	13	43.3	2	6.7
	Neutral	1	3.3	2	6.7
	Agree	5	16.7	4	13.3
	Strongly Agree	2	6.7	16	53.3
	Total	30	100.0	30	100.0

Source: Field Data, November, 2020

With a mean score of 3.76 and a standard deviation of 1.633, data in Table 4.33 reveals that 22 (73.3%) public school teachers either strongly disagree or disagree that instructional supervision is time consuming but 46 (66.6%) private school teachers (mean score 2.26; st. deviation 1.257) thought otherwise.

Table 4.34: Instructional supervision interferes with teaching and learning processes

	Scale	Public		Private	
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	0	0.0	3	10.0
	Disagree	2	6.7	1	3.3
	Neutral	0	0.0	0	0.0
	Agree	10	33.3	6	20.0
	Strongly Agree	18	60.0	20	66.7
	Total	30	100.0	30	100.0

Source: Field Data, November, 2020

Moreover, results presented in Table 4.34 shows an agreement in the views expressed by teachers of both sides. The results indicates that 10 (33.3%) public school teachers agree and 18 (60%) of them strongly agree with a mean score of 4.40 and st. deviation of 1.290 that instructional supervision interferes with teaching and learning processes, however, 26 (86.7%) private school teachers (mean score of 4.466 and st. deviation of .810) either strongly agree or agree to the above assertion.

Table 4.35: Poor headteacher-teacher relationship affect the effectiveness of instructional supervision

	Scale	Public		Private	
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Valid	Disagree	2	6.7	0	0.0
	Neutral	0	0.0	0	0.0
	Agree	13	43.3	11	36.7

Strongly Agree	15	50.0	19	63.3
Total	30	100.0	30	100.0

Source: Field Data, November, 2020

According to Table 4.35, 28 (93.3%) of public school teachers with a mean score of 4.63, st. deviation of .490 either strongly agree or agree that poor headteacher-teacher relationship affect the effectiveness of instructional supervision. The responses of the private school teachers were not different. All (100%) of them (mean score 4.36; st. deviation .808) also agree that poor headteacher-teacher relationship affect the effectiveness of instructional supervision.

Table 4.36: Headteachers lack supervisory tools, funds and materials

Valid	Scale	Public		Private	
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
	Strongly Disagree	0	0.0	13	43.3
	Disagree	0	0.0	10	33.3
	Neutral	3	10.0	3	10.0
	Agree	6	20.0	0	0.0
	Strongly Agree	21	70.0	4	13.3
	Total	30	100.0	30	100.0

Source: Field Data, November, 2020

In Table 4.36, 6 (20%) public school teachers agree and 21 (70%) others strongly agree (mean score of 2.07; st. deviation of 1.33) that headteachers lack supervisory tools, funds and materials, meanwhile, 23 (76.6%) private school teachers strongly disagree (mean score 4.60; st. deviation .674).

Discussion

Data gathered revealed that 100% of both public school teachers (mean score 4.70; st. deviation .466) and private school teachers (mean score 4.56; st. deviation .504) admitted that they regularly supervise pupils works (exercise, assignment and projects, etc). Another agreement was recorded where all (100%) the respondents (public school teachers with a mean score of 4.63 and a standard deviation of .490 and private school teachers with a mean score of 4.86 and a standard deviation of .345) disagree that pupils are involved in decision making on matters affecting them.

Furthermore, the information presented suggests that with a mean score of 3.83 and a standard deviation of 1.366, 76.6% of the public school teachers held the same view with 80% of the private school teachers (mean score 4.06; st. deviation 1.460) that pupils are motivated by teachers and school authorities. Additionally, both (100%) public school teachers (mean score 4.53; st. deviation .507) and private school teachers (mean score 4.83; st. deviation .379) admitted that pupils are disciplined by teachers and school authorities. Moreover, the results specifies that 100% of all the respondents (public school teachers with a mean score of 4.63 and a standard deviation of .490) and private school teachers (mean score of 4.86 and a standard deviation of .345) were certain that pupils are given constant feedback on their performance.

Again, with a mean score of 4.70 and standard deviation of .466, 100% of the public school teachers denote that pupils are actively involved in class activities and this was again seconded by all (100%) the private school teachers with a mean score of 4.70 and standard deviation of .466. Similarly, the data reveals that 100% of public teachers with a mean score of 4.06 and a standard deviation of 1.387 agree that teachers use instructional time effectively and this was also agreed by 80% of private school teachers also with a mean score of 4.90 and standard deviation of .305. Meanwhile, the data presents some disagreements in the results. For instance, data reveals that 73.3% of the public school teachers with a mean score of 3.50 and standard deviation of 1.502) disagree that TLMs are used in the classroom, however, more than half (66.7%) of the private school teachers with a mean score of 2.20 and standard deviation of 1.627) maintain that pupils are taught with TLMs. Also,

while a huge percentage (86.7%) of the public school teachers (mean score 4.83; st. deviation .379) disagree that pupils are given the opportunity to manipulate TLMs in class, all (100%) the private school teachers with a mean score of 1.83 and standard deviation of .647) agree that pupils are given the opportunity to manipulate TLMs in class.

Besides, with a mean of 4.03 and standard deviation of 1.37, majority (56.7%) of public school teachers disagree that pupils are motivated by parents, however, 80% of private school teachers with mean score of 2.43 and standard deviation of 1.612 were of the view that pupils are motivated by parents. Also, the study found out that 66% of public school teachers (mean score 4.83; st. deviation .379) strongly disagree that pupils have access to school facilities like library and laboratories, however, all the (100%) the private school teachers (mean score 2.20; st. deviation 1.749) agree pupils have access to school facilities like library and laboratories.

Studies (Blasé and Blasé, 2004; Costa, 2017; Fraenkel, 2016 and Qayyum et al., 2015) over the years have supported these findings. Blasé and Blasé (2004) for instance denote that children need regular supervision and monitoring of work given to them. Moreover, Costa (2017) agreed with Fraenkel (2016) that related to these developmental and cognitive processes is the issue of motivation for learning. Fraenkel (2016) said students will work harder to achieve understanding and will make greater progress when they are motivated to learn something. However, motivation is not just inherent in the individual; it can be developed by skillful teaching and mentoring (Fraenkel, 2016; Costa, 2017).

With a mean score of 4.33 and standard deviation of .884, 60% of the public school teachers agree teachers have negative perception towards supervisory practices in the school and this was again seconded by 73% of the private school teachers with a mean score of 3.80 and standard deviation of 1.540. Similarly, another agreement was seen where 63.3% of the public school teachers maintained (mean 4.133, st. deviation .973) that most teachers do not cooperate with headteachers during supervision and this was supported by 73.4% of the private school teachers with a mean score of 3.63 and a standard deviation of 1.519.

Additionally, information presented posit that majority (83.3%) of the public teachers (mean 3.50; st. deviation 1.525) affirmed that some headteachers' are not effective in carrying out instructional supervision, meanwhile, the same view was held by a huge percentage (63.4%) of the private school teachers with a mean score of 4.033; st. deviation of 1.376. Moreover, the results indicates that a huge percentage of both respondents (93.3% of the public school teachers agree with a mean score of 4.40 and st. deviation of 1.290) and 86.7% of private school teachers also with a mean score of 4.466 and a standard deviation of .810) admitted that instructional supervision interferes with teaching and learning processes.

Likewise, most (93.3%) of public school teachers with a mean score of 4.63, st. deviation of .490 affirmed that poor headteacher-teacher relationship affect the effectiveness of instructional supervision, meanwhile, a similar view was held by all (100%) the teachers from the private schools (mean score 4.36; st. deviation .808).

Meanwhile, 90% of the public school teachers (mean score of 2.07; st. deviation of 1.33) acknowledged that headteachers lack supervisory tools, funds and materials, but more than half (76.6%) of the private school teachers strongly disagree (mean score 4.60; st. deviation .674).

The study observed that both public school teachers (73.4% with a mean score of 4.33 and st. deviation of 1.295) and private school teachers (86.7% with a mean score of 3.63 and standard deviation of 1.325) agree that teachers are regularly supervised by headteacher and officers. Again, with a mean score of 4.70 and a standard deviation of .466 for public school teachers and a mean score of 4.86 and standard deviation of .345 for private school teachers, all (100%) the respondents affirmed that they are given enough room to perform their duties without tension. Similarly, 100% of public school teachers (mean score 3.53; st. deviation 1.795) and 60% of private school teachers (mean score 3.53; st. deviation 1.795) admitted that they are involved in decision making on matters affecting the school. Likewise, the study discovered that 86.6% of public school teachers with a mean score of 4.70 and standard deviation of .466 and 83.3% and private school teachers also with a mean score of 4.86 and standard deviation of .345 denied that teachers are motivated by school leadership.

Also, the data observed a disparity in the views expressed by the respondents. While, 73.4% of the public school teachers (mean score 4.13; st. deviation 1.279) claimed they are not given feedback on supervision but on the contrary, most (66.7%) of the private school teachers with a mean score of 2.03 and standard deviation of 1.033 acknowledged that they are given feedback on supervision. While 80% of the public school teachers (mean score 3.7667 and standard deviation 1.67504) denied the fact that TLMs are available for them, 66.7% of the private school teachers with a mean score of 1.83 and standard deviation 1.176 confirmed that TLMs are available for them to use in the school.

5.1.2 Opportunities and support given to pupils in performing their instructional supervisory roles in public and private basic schools in Koforidua

Data gathered revealed that 100% of both public school teachers (mean score 4.70; st. deviation .466) and private school teachers (mean score 4.56; st. deviation .504) admitted that they regularly supervise pupils works (exercise, assignment and projects, etc). Another agreement was recorded where all (100%) the respondents (public school teachers with a mean score of 4.63 and a standard deviation of .490 and private school teachers with a mean score of 4.86 and a standard deviation of .345) disagree that pupils are involved in decision making on matters affecting them. Furthermore, the information presented suggests that with a mean score of 3.83 and a standard deviation of 1.366, 76.6% of the public school teachers held the same view with 80% of the private school teachers (mean score 4.06; st. deviation 1.460) that pupils are motivated by teachers and school authorities.

Additionally, both (100%) public school teachers (mean score 4.53; st. deviation .507) and private school teachers (mean score 4.83; st. deviation .379) admitted that pupils are disciplined by teachers and school authorities. Moreover, the results specifies that 100% of all the respondents (public school teachers with a mean score of 4.63 and a standard deviation of .490) and private school teachers (mean score of 4.86 and a standard deviation of .345) were certain that teachers are given the opportunity to share ideas among themselves. Again, with a mean score of 4.70 and standard deviation of .466, 100% of the public school teachers denote that pupils are actively involved in class activities and this was again seconded by all (100%) the private school teachers with a mean score of 4.70 and standard deviation of .466. Lastly, the data reveals that 100% of public teachers with a mean score of 4.06 and a standard deviation of 1.387 agree that teachers use instructional time effectively and this was also agreed by 80% of private school teachers also with a mean score of 4.90 and standard deviation of .305.

Meanwhile, the study presents some disagreements in the results. For instance, data reveals that 73.3% of the public school teachers with a mean score of 3.50 and standard deviation of 1.502) disagree that Teaching and Learning Materials (TLMs) are used in the classroom, however, more than half (66.7%) of the private school teachers with a mean score of 2.20 and standard deviation of 1.627) maintain that pupils are taught with TLMs. Also, while a huge percentage (86.7%) of the public school teachers (mean score 4.83; st. deviation .379) disagree that pupils are given the opportunity to manipulate TLMs in class, all (100%) the private school teachers with a mean score of 1.83 and standard deviation of .647) agree that pupils are given the opportunity to manipulate TLMs in class.

Similarly, with a mean of 4.03 and standard deviation of 1.37, majority (56.7%) of public school teachers disagree that pupils are motivated by parents, however, 80% of private school teachers with mean score of 2.43 and standard deviation of 1.612 were of the view that pupils are motivated by parents. Furthermore, the study found out that 66% of public school teachers (mean score 4.83; st. deviation .379) strongly disagree that pupils have access to school facilities like library and laboratories, however, all the (100%) the private school teachers (mean score 2.20; st. deviation 1.749) agree pupils have access to school facilities like library and laboratories. With a mean score of 4.33 and standard deviation of .884, 60% of the public school teachers agree teachers have negative perception towards supervisory practices in the school and this was again seconded by 73% of the

private school teachers with a mean score of 3.80 and standard deviation of 1.540. Similarly, another agreement was seen where 63.3% of the public school teachers maintained (mean 4.133, st. deviation .973) that most teachers do not cooperate with headteachers during supervision and this was supported by 73.4% of the private school teachers with a mean score of 3.63 and a standard deviation of 1.519.

Additionally, information presented posit that majority (83.3%) of the public teachers (mean 3.50; st. deviation 1.525) affirmed that some headteachers' are not effective in carrying out instructional supervision, meanwhile, the same view was held by a huge percentage (63.4%) of the private school teachers with a mean score of 4.033; st. deviation of 1.376. Moreover, the results indicates that a huge percentage of both respondents (93.3% of the public school teachers agree with a mean score of 4.40 and st. deviation of 1.290) and 86.7% of private school teachers also with a mean score of 4.466 and a standard deviation of .810) admitted that instructional supervision interferes with teaching and learning processes.

Likewise, most (93.3%) of public school teachers with a mean score of 4.63, st. deviation of .490 affirmed that poor headteacher-teacher relationship affect the effectiveness of instructional supervision, meanwhile, a similar view was held by all (100%) the teachers from the private schools (mean score 4.36; st. deviation .808). Meanwhile, 90% of the public school teachers (mean score of 2.07; st. deviation of 1.33) acknowledged that headteachers lack supervisory tools, funds and materials, but more than half (76.6%) of the private school teachers strongly disagree (mean score 4.60; st. deviation .674). Another disagree with was seen where 73.3% of the public school teachers (with a mean score of 3.76 and a standard deviation of 1.633) disagree that instructional supervision is time consuming but 66.6% of the private school teachers (mean score 2.26; st. deviation 1.257) thought otherwise.

Conclusions

On the differences in classroom support given to teachers in the public and private basic schools in Koforidua, the study found out that; (a) public school teachers are not given feedback on supervision but their counterparts at the private sector are given feedback on supervision and (b) TLMs are not available for public school teachers but available for private school teachers as mentioned by the respondents and so the study concluded that the differences in classroom support given to teachers in the public and private basic schools in Koforidua were that teachers in private schools receive feedback on supervision and also TLMs are available for use in the classroom.

Again, on the opportunities and support given to pupils in performing their instructional supervisory roles in public and private basic schools in Koforidua, it was observed that private school pupils are taught with TLMs and have opportunity to manipulate TLMs in class, have access to school facilities and are motivated by parents but this is lacking in the public schools. As a result, the study concluded that public school pupils lack some opportunities and support such as learning with and manipulating TLMs, access to school facilities and motivation from parents.

On the differences in training opportunities created for the teachers in public and private basic schools in Koforidua, the study found that; (a) teachers are given the opportunity to share ideas among themselves, (b) in-service training are not regular organized for teachers and (c) teachers are sponsored by the school to attend workshops and seminars and are also permitted to pursue further studies and so there were no differences in training opportunities created for the teachers in public and private basic schools in Koforidua.

Finally, on challenges faced by headteachers' in carrying out instructional supervision in public and private basic schools in Koforidua, the study concluded that; teachers have negative perception towards supervisory practices in the school and so do not cooperate with headteachers' during supervision, some headteachers' are

not effective in carrying out instructional supervision, instructional supervision interferes with teaching and learning processes, poor headteacher-teacher relationship affect the effectiveness of instructional supervision.

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